

Theory of Change: Mechanism Maps of Agricultural Innovations in Rural Scotland

Scottish Government Strategic Research Programme 2022-27: KJHI-B1-3 Milestone 4.2.2
March 2026

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Executive summary

In Scottish remote regions, the availability and accessibility of fresh and affordable fruits and vegetables (F&Vs) remains a challenge. This is particularly true for islands, due to unsuitable growing conditions – soil and climate – and unreliable and lengthy transport networks causing the products to reach consumers close to the end of their shelf life. Indoor and hybrid growing could represent a viable solution, but the introduction of advanced technology in small communities with fragmented value chains calls for sound ex-ante assessment. We focus on the case of the **Orkney Islands**, characterised by stronger farming traditions compared to other islands, and on two innovations. The first one is a **vertical farm** (VF), already proposed as part of the Islands Growth Deal in 2022, but with no progress to date. The second are aeroponic **Tower Farms**[®] to be installed in **Polycrubs**[®] (polytunnels adapted to the local windy conditions), which are being trialled by local researchers. These two innovations differ in terms of the scale of the required investments, energy demand, level of control over the growing conditions (and thus capacity to maintain produce quality), and level of centralisation (and thus the capacity to fulfil the needs of scattered communities). Nevertheless, they share the advantage of making use of the energy coming from the many Orkney windfarms, currently curtailed.

Building on interviews with local stakeholders, we develop **Theory of Change Mechanism Maps** of the two innovations, framed as “interventions.” After identifying their long-term goal, we break down each intervention into constituting actions, define the causal pathways triggered by these actions, the baseline assumptions underpinning them, and how these are affected by external conditions. These will be used to develop likely scenarios of deploying the innovations, together with local stakeholders.

Highlights

- A VF could boost the overall **food economy** of the Orkney Islands but requires establishing **collaborations** with businesses upstream and downstream, and identification of a managing organisation.
- Promoting the installation of Tower Farms in Polycrubs would improve **self-sufficiency in F&Vs**, and generate broader social and environmental benefits, but the financial viability remains uncertain.
- The centralised nature of a VF would not solve the issue of accessing fresh F&Vs in the **Outer Islands**, since the infrastructure would be installed on the Mainland, different from the Tower Farms.
- The direct use of **curtailed energy** remains a challenge due to current regulations, but the possibility of developing a smart grid or cost compensation mechanisms is key for financial competitiveness.
- Large **retail chain supermarkets** (Tesco and Lidl) are unlikely to be interested in VF produce because they already have established relations with external suppliers. Collaboration opportunities should be explored, but they require competitive prices, only achievable through cheap energy.
- **Acceptability** of the produce grown in VFs or Tower Farms is not an issue, especially thanks to local origin; however, the VF infrastructure can face acceptability due to landscape modification.
- Both innovations would create **dependence** from external technology and input providers.

1 Introduction

This milestone is part of Activity 4.2 “*Ex-ante assessment of the impact of novel crops and farming techniques on rural territories*” of the Scottish Government’s funded project JHI-B1-3 “*The impact of novel crops and farming practices on the Scottish agricultural landscape.*” Activity 4.2 investigates the potential impact of agricultural innovation on local food systems in rural Scotland. The **Orkney Islands** were chosen as the case study; **vertical farming**, and aeroponic **Tower Farms**¹ to be installed in **Polycrubs**² represent the innovations of interest. This milestone, in particular, presents **Theories of Change (ToC)** and **Mechanism Maps (MM)** developed for each innovation by the research team based on interviews with local stakeholders and a workshop conducted at the Orkney Science Festival in September 2025 (Dinnie *et al.*, 2026). The ToC MM will be validated with local stakeholders, and discussed in a second workshop, tentatively at the Orkney Science Festival 2026, where scenarios (“most plausible negative,” and “most plausible positive”) from deploying the innovations locally will be also developed.

Our approach builds on the methodology illustrated in Piras *et al.* (2022), which in turn is based on the H2020 project RELOCAL.³ RELOCAL sought to assess whether spatial justice could be achieved through place-based interventions, many of which implemented in peripheral rural territories. For instance, the Scottish case study in RELOCAL focused on “*Strengthening Communities*,” an intervention led by Highland & Island Enterprise which entailed community land buyouts on the Isle of Lewis. Hence, the methodology is well-suited for analysing innovation *as interventions* aimed at boosting the local food economy and the social fabric surrounding it in the Orkney Islands. Nevertheless, we deviate from the methodology inasmuch we do not aim to investigate how different underlying place-based scenarios will impact the viability of interventions but rather, how each intervention will impact place-based scenarios.

ToC is a policy design and evaluation tool that “*emphasises the need to clearly specify the ‘internal’ logic underpinning an intervention, that is, the rationale behind it and the causal pathway(s) from the initial input to the final impact under certain assumptions*” (Piras *et al.*, 2022: 954). The MM compares the ToC against underlying contextual conditions and drivers. Therefore, its incorporation in the ToC allows us to consider both its “internal” consistency, and “external” validity, and how the baseline assumptions underpinning the ToCs’ causal pathways depend on these contextual conditions and drivers. While we develop one ToC per intervention, the place considered for their implementation is the same; therefore, the MM is common to both. Equally, the final outcome of achieving “*just and self-sustaining local food systems for rural Scotland*,” which is beyond the accountability ceiling and requires several interrelated interventions over a long period, is shared by both.

The rest of the report is structured as follows. Section 2 presents the ToC for the vertical farm; Section 3 does the same for the aeroponic Tower Farms; Section 3.3 presents the MM common to both. Finally, Section 5 concludes by reflecting on how the baseline assumptions underpinning the ToCs’ causal pathways are affected by the MM’s contextual conditions and drivers.

¹ See <https://www.towerfarms.com/> [accessed 25 February 2026].

² See <https://www.polycrub.co.uk/> [accessed 25 February 2026].

³ “Resituating the local in cohesion and territorial development” (2016-2021), <https://relocal.eu/> [accessed 25 February 2026].

2 Theory of Change – Vertical Farm

Vertical farms (VFs) are an example of controlled environment agriculture. In a VF, crops are typically grown in vertically stacked layers or structures within a controlled indoor space. The growing environment is managed to optimise temperature, humidity, light, and nutrient delivery. The soil may be replaced with nutrient-rich water, ensuring that roots receive the essential minerals for growth, or with a solid growing medium, with coconut coir being a popular option. Artificial lighting, such as LED lights, is generally used to replicate sunlight, and this lighting is finely tuned to meet the specific needs of each crop. VFs are suited to growing a wide variety of crops, especially leafy greens, and herbs, such as lettuce, spinach, kale, basil, and parsley, as well as fruits, like strawberries.

Compared to traditional farming in open fields, VFs allow the saving of resources such as soil and water in food production. They also allow production of fresh vegetables in regions which, like the Orkney Islands, would otherwise not be suitable due to climatic and soil conditions – thus improving access to food in space and time. However, while reducing the need for soil and water, VFs rely heavily on energy, which can lead to environmental strain if they do not use renewable energy sources. The Orkney Islands have a wealth of wind energy that can be potentially used to overcome this challenge.

Based on the above considerations, an “Orkney vertical farm” project has been conceived as part of the Islands Growth Deal in 2022, and £2 million have been allocated for this purpose. Nevertheless, there have been limited advancement since then.⁴ While a potential technology provider has been identified, concretely developing the VF would entail acquiring land for building the physical structure, and identifying (or setting up) an organisation to manage it. Accordingly, the first intervention considered in this report is *the development of a vertical farm in the Orkney Island*. The respective ToC MM is presented in Figure 1 below, while the elements constituting the ToC are described in the following section.

2.1. The Long-term Outcome/Goal

The long-term outcome of our intervention, specified in a blue box at the top of the ToC diagram, goes beyond the VF as a viable income generating business – although financial sustainability is a necessary long-term condition for success – and consists of *thriving the overall food economy of the Orkney Islands* by increasing local food production capacity and consequently, reducing dependence on imports from outside the islands. This is an economy- rather than community-focused project, which aspired to generating broader financial benefits beyond the VF itself, through trickle down. For this to happen, both downstream and upstream value chain stakeholders must be mobilised.

2.2. The Intervention and its Constituent Actions

The intervention consists in *developing a vertical farm business in the Orkney Islands*, and includes **three** constituent actions, represented by numbered orange squares in the ToC diagram. These actions must be deployed in parallel in order to deliver the long-term goal,⁵ and they trigger the development of as many interconnected pathways, explained in detail in Section 2.3. The constituent actions are:

⁴ See this article in the local press: <https://www.pressandjournal.co.uk/fp/news/highlands-islands/3929712/vertical-farm-project-on-orkney-back-on-track/> [accessed 24 February 2026], or this report of the Orkney Council’s sub-committee meeting: <https://www.orkney.gov.uk/media/exsexvk0/item-9-vertical-farm.pdf> [accessed 24 February 2026].

⁵ Both here and in the ToC of the aeroponic Tower Farms, the numbers assigned to the constituent actions, as well as the letters and numbers assigned to the baseline assumptions and contextual conditions, respectively, should not be interpreted as implying a chronological order. The only temporal consequentiality is indicated by the arrows connecting the intermediate outcomes that constitute the causal pathways.

- i. *The promotion of a stable local **demand** for vertical farm products.* This action focuses on the demand side, since a stable demand is key for generating a sustained income stream and thus ensuring the viability of the VF as well as connected food businesses (processors, retailers, etc.).
- ii. *The development of the vertical farm **infrastructure**.* This action focuses on the supply side through the establishment of the physical and organisational infrastructure to ensure a steady production.
- iii. *The building of a **value chain** for vertical farm products.* The VF business would need to establish working relations with existing food businesses or promote the establishment of new businesses, upstream and downstream, to be able to meet consumers' demand.

2.3. Intermediate Outcomes and Causal Pathways

The three components of the intervention can be seen as the starting points for as many causal pathways: one related to creating the conditions for a stable consumer demand; one related to developing the infrastructure; and one related to the building of the value chain, from production to consumption. The causal pathways are chains of intermediate outcomes (green boxes in the ToC diagram) connected by red arrows. Thicker arrows indicate more robust relations, while dashed ones identify relations that are weaker and more uncertain, and therefore strongly conditional on the baseline assumptions.

Promotion of a stable demand

The initial step of the first causal pathway would be to achieve acceptance of vertical farming products by local consumers. While previous research within this same project showed that this is not likely to be a major issue among Scottish consumers (Mzek *et al.*, 2025), this must not be overlooked, and may require awareness building. Achieving acceptance of VF products, and its recognition by local retailers, would result in regular availability of the (accepted) products on their shelves. In turn, availability would lead to the replacement of equivalent vegetable products imported from outside the Orkney Islands, and consequently, to healthier and more localised consumer diets, boosting the Orkney food economy. The passage from the replacement of imported products to healthier local diets is more uncertain since consumers' choices depend on a range of factors that are external to this specific ToC. Additionally, the regular availability of products is conditional on viable VF infrastructure, achieved through the second causal pathway, and on working collaborations between the VF business and local processors and distributors, resulting from the third pathway. Finally, consumers' diets would also benefit from procurement agreements with the Ho.Re.Ca. (Hotel, Restaurant, Catering) and public sectors, beyond retailers.

Development of the infrastructure

The second causal pathway starts with the identification of a space (land) where the physical VF infrastructure can be built, possibly in Kirkwall, the main town in the Orkney Island, located at the centre of Orkney Mainland, where most of the Orkney population live. Once this space is identified and acquired, or rented, an organisation (business) to run the facility can be set up, which will oversee the building of the physical infrastructure. The interviews suggested that identifying a managing organisation is challenging because of the small local market, and the identification of a physical space will not necessarily push a local entity to undertaking this role. Once the infrastructure is built, the business can start operating, providing jobs (and thus income) as well as vegetable outputs for the local food economy. This latter intermediate outcome (a running infrastructure) is conditional on viable upstream stages of the value chain that can provide access to production inputs –intermediate outcome of the last causal pathway – and conditions the availability of products at retailers. However, retailers may supply themselves elsewhere despite local availability of VF products; therefore, this last relationship is uncertain.

Building of a value chain

The third causal pathway entails integration with other firms both upstream and downstream. The first step is to have adequate access to production inputs (nutrients, and the technology) locally. Once this

is achieved, and thus the VF is up and running – a robust relationship with an intermediate outcome of the previous pathway – viable collaborations with processors (e.g., packaging) and distributors can be established. Such collaborations would make it possible to supply retailers – as part of the first pathway – and to set up procurement procedures with large users in the public sector, like schools or the Kirkwall hospital, as well as Ho.Re.Ca. companies (particularly for supplying the tourist economy, which benefits from a booming cruise sector). These large users would ensure a regular demand, and thus income, to the VF business, and widespread and regular consumption, triggering a more robust pathway towards the long-term goal of boosting the Orkney food economy.

2.4. Baseline Assumptions

In the process of collecting evidence from stakeholders, there was awareness that some of the internal “contingencies” were factors which facilitated the causal pathways (named “*promoters*”), while others acted as “*inhibitors*”, making the deployment of the causal pathways outlined above more difficult. In the ToC diagram in Figure 1, both promoters and inhibitors are represented by blue circles, located in correspondence of the intermediate outcome(s) which are conditional on them. Baseline assumptions refer to facilitating factors operating properly, as well as the absence of inhibitors.

- A.** *Procurement procedures can be established only if large users (the public, and Ho.Re.Ca. sectors) are **interested** in vertical farm products.* At the moment, retailers like Tesco (the main supermarket in Kirkwall, where most local consumers allegedly shop for food, and which could not be contacted as part of this study) are not, since they have well-established agreements with non-Orkney suppliers. Equally, the cruise industry, which could potentially result in sustained demand for fresh, local vegetables, procures all food elsewhere at the start of the cruise trip.
- B. **Acceptance**** by local consumers and the resulting inclusion of VF produce within local diets are conditional on the produce being perceived as “local” – which cannot be taken for granted, given that the VF does not use local soil or other resources – and that “food neophobia” is not an issue – based on a large-scale survey conducted across Scotland (Mzek *et al.*, 2025), this should not be an issue.
- C.** For final consumers, retailers, and the public and the Ho.Re.Ca. sectors to be willing to purchase VF products, their attributes, but primarily their price, must be **competitive** with those of current non-Orkney suppliers: this will depend on the cost of the technology and other inputs, primarily energy.
- D.** Closely related to the previous assumption, due to the significant **energy** requirement of a VF, for a business to remain viable, energy must be reliably available, and directly accessible by the managing organisation, at low cost. Despite the assumptions motivating the VF project in the Island Growth Deal, our interviewees found that it is not necessarily the case, due to current regulations requiring energy producers to sell it to the national grid. Alternatively, if the same business were to manage both the VF, and wind turbines, the cost of the energy exported to the grid would offset the cost of the energy used in the VF. Or it might be possible to set up a “smart grid” (i.e., a closed system) so that energy produced locally is also used locally (i.e., for the VF). Either way, if wind energy is used, this “green” energy would displace at least some of the fossil fuel energy (diesel, compost) used in conventional farming, thus contributing to net-zero emissions goals.
- E.** In order to have a VF infrastructure up and running, it is key that production **inputs** (i.e., nutrients, lights, and other equipment) as well as technical assistance are available locally, or can be procured elsewhere. High transport costs of ferry or air travel mean that this may not necessarily be the case.
- F.** To develop and manage the infrastructure, it is necessary to identify a local **organisation** interested in this role, or set up one from scratch, and hire and train staff to work within the organisation. The interviews highlighted that this is challenging: to date, no local organisation has expressed an interest in managing the VF for which the Island Growth Deal funding has been acquired.
- G.** Another assumption is that a suitable **site** for developing the VF infrastructure is available in Kirkwall,

and can be purchased, rented, or otherwise acquired by the managing organisation. Our interviews suggested that some spaces may be available, but no agreement has been negotiated in this regard.

- H.** An assumption closely related to the previous one, since it impacts the possibility of devoting a space to the VF infrastructure, is that the building project meets no significant issues in terms of community **acceptance** or **planning** restrictions. Some interviewees raised the issue that a large building to host the VF may be perceived as incongruent with the local built environment and landscape.
- I.** Adding to the above, the Orkney **climate** (primarily the wind conditions) could represent a technical obstacle to building such a tall infrastructure; no definite answers could be obtained in this regard.
- J.** Access to fresh vegetables is an issue in Orkney Mainland, but even more in the Outer Islands. Since the VF is meant to be developed in Kirkwall, where most of the Orkney population are based, functional **transport links** from Orkney Mainland to the Outer Islands are still required in order for this intervention to generate widespread effects on the Orkney food economy. Currently, ferry links are unreliable due to weather disruptions, and are unlikely to improve as a result of this project.
- K.** A VF infrastructure requires significant initial investment, as reflected in the allocation of £2 million for capital expenditure as part of the Island Growth Deal. A key assumption for keeping the project attractive to a potential managing organisation is that this **funding** remains available, or alternative, comparable funding opportunities emerge. However, some interviewees highlight that the deadline for using this money was approaching at the end of 2025.
- L.** Reaching consumers requires that vegetables (likely leafy greens) produced in the VF are **processed, packaged, and distributed**. From our interviews, we could not determine whether these operations are expected to be all internalised by the prospective managing organisation, or it is necessary that other businesses are available (or established) locally to carry them. We assume that these entities are either available (and interested) or can be easily established.
- M.** Finally, in order for VF products to be introduced in the market, they must comply with **food quality and safety regulations**. Based on our interviews, we have no reasons to doubt of this; nevertheless, due diligence is still required, and making the necessary initial checks can be demanding, and costly.

Figure 1. Theory of Change Mechanism Map for the development of vertical farming in the Orkney Islands.

3 Theory of Change – Aeroponic Tower Farms

Aeroponics **Tower Farms** are vertical growing systems that produce plants without soil, using a nutrient-rich water solution that circulates through stacked “towers.” Differently from the VF, the growing environment (temperature, light) is not fully controlled; nevertheless, they allow to save soil and water, and to increase the growing space through expanding it vertically. These towers require minimal setup and maintenance, and can be installed either indoors or outdoors. The idea promoted by the Agronomy Institute of the Orkney College is to install them within Orkneys’ **Polycrubs**. Polycrubs are very strong, wind-resistant polytunnels with an aerodynamic curved shape that were first conceived as a community project in the Shetland Islands, whose climate is very similar to the Orkneys’, in 2008. Since then, they have been adopted by many entities in the private, public, and third sectors around the Orkney Islands, including Kirkwall hospital, schools, Community Development Trusts (many of them based in the Outer Islands), care homes, etc. These entities are interested in small supplies of fresh F&Vs either for their own use (hospital, schools), or for community wealth building (Development Trusts), or even for sale (e.g., Community Trusts that manage small shops or cafés, especially in the Outer Islands).

Accordingly, the intervention considered here is to **promote the adoption of aeroponic Tower Farms in Polycrubs across the Orkney Islands**, targeting different type of public, private, and third-sector users. The respective ToC MM is presented in Figure 2 below, with the intervention named in the yellow box at the bottom of the diagram, and the elements constituting the ToC are described in the following.

3.1. The Long-term Outcome/Goal

Differently from the VF, the aeroponic Tower Farms are a lower-cost innovation which can potentially be adopted by small organisations, thus generating diffused benefits through equally diffused adoption. Therefore, the long-term goal is to **improve self-sufficiency in terms of fresh vegetables** (primarily leafy greens) **across Orkneys** by creating community-based local food systems that reduce dependence on imports. This objective is community- rather than economy-focused, although it may generate income opportunities too, and is entered in the blue box at the top of the ToC diagram. For this objective to be achieved, existing organisations in the public, private, and community sectors must be mobilised.

3.2. The Intervention and its Constituent Actions

The intervention consists in *promoting the adoption of aeroponic Tower Farms in Polycrubs* by several organisations (public, private, third sector) across the Orkney Islands, with a particular focus on peripheral locations (Outer Islands) which, while producing their own F&Vs, face issues in terms of seasonality and may be interested in expanding the range of products grown, or increasing their supply for market and wellbeing reasons. This intervention consists of **two** constituent actions which, similarly to the VF, trigger as many closely intertwined pathways, described in detail in Section 2.33.3, namely:

- i. *Making the Tower Farm **technology** locally available to potential adopters.* This action focuses on the “hard” element of the intervention, i.e., the provision of the hardware technology – the Tower Farms proper – to potential adopters around the archipelago. The Agronomy Institute of the Orkney College has installed some Tower Farms in their venue, as a demonstration site, and is in contact with the technology provider, who can be introduced to other prospective adopters.
- ii. *Building the **knowledge** and evidence bases for widespread adoption.* This second action focuses on the “soft” element of the intervention, i.e., building of awareness among prospective adopters and, subsequently, the skills and knowledge necessary to install and manage the Tower Farms.

Figure 2. Theory of Change Mechanism Map for the promotion of aeroponic Tower Farms in the Orkney Islands.

3.3. Intermediate Outcomes and Causal Pathways

The two components of the intervention represent the starting points for as many causal pathways: one (on the left of the diagram in Figure 2) related the hard, physical component; and one (on the right) related to the soft, capacity-building component. The intermediate outcomes are again represented by green boxes connected by red arrows – thicker for more robust relations, dashed for relations that are weaker and more uncertain. Below, we detail the chains of intermediate outcome.

Making the Tower Farm technology available

The initial step of the first pathway would be for enough local organisations (local Development Trusts, small businesses) to obtain funding to purchase the technology, which although more affordable than a VF structure, is still costly from small organisations. This stepping stone would lead to both the Tower Farms being installed in Polycrubs locally, and employees (gardeners) being hired for managing them: although creating local employment is not the main goal of the intervention, it would represent an important positive spillover for the communities involved. Achieving these two intermediate outcomes would result in a regular supply of fresh vegetables which, in the presence of a corresponding demand (generated by the second branch of the intervention) would lead to the establishment of short value chains for fresh vegetables, and subsequently to the long-term goal. We do not foresee strong uncertainties in the logic of this first pathway, and the relationship between the installation of the equipment and the hiring of employees on the one hand, and regular supply of products on the other hand, looks particularly robust, given the pressure for financial viability that the former outcomes would generate.

Building the knowledge and evidence base on Tower Farms

The first step of the pathway arising from the “soft” action is for potential producers to gain knowledge of the innovative idea (Tower Farms to be installed in Polycrubs), which would be achieved, for instance, through the demonstration being conducted at the Agronomy Institute. From potential producers, this knowledge would trickle down to potential buyers (e.g., cafés, independent shops, local Coops) as well as local consumers, resulting in a regular demand for fresh vegetables and consequently, in the establishment of short value chains, in turn leading to the long-term goal. While some of these intermediate buyers can be public organisations (schools, the NHS) or independent businesses (restaurants, shops), in some cases, the same entity acts as both producer and seller: this is the case of local Development Trusts managing cafés or shops in the Outer Islands. In this case, the pathway between awareness and selling is immediate. Otherwise, the paths from potential producers gaining awareness and interest, to sellers and consumers acting accordingly, remain uncertain due to profitability issues or lack of interest.

The two causal pathways interact at various stages. First, producers gaining knowledge of the innovative idea is a prerequisite for them to apply for, and possibly obtain funding for the Tower Farms infrastructure. Second, for local users to purchase (or anyway acquire) the products, a regular supply of vegetables must be established. Third, the viability of short value chains is conditional on both supply (left branch) and demand (right side) being established. These linkages across branches are all robust.

3.4. Baseline Assumptions

In this last section, we present the “*promoters*” and “*inhibitors*” acting as baseline assumptions for the pathways activated by the intervention. As in the ToC of the VF, also in the ToC diagram in Figure 2, they are represented as blue circles positioned next to the intermediate outcomes that depend on them. Some of these assumptions are similar to those underpinning the previous ToC.

- A.** Public **funding** is available for local organisations (Development Trusts, small businesses) to initiate the project. Although the expected costs are lower than for establishing a VF, they are still significant for small organisations, especially if not profit-oriented (for instance, the cost of the demonstration

at the Agronomy College was around £48,000). Therefore, public funding or, alternatively, competitive funding provided by private or third-sector entities is key to offset the initial investment (equipment) cost, and possibly to cover management costs like the salary of part- or full-time gardeners.

- B.** Enough local organisations across the Orkney Islands are **interested** in the project. A key component of the intervention is its diffused nature, i.e., the fact that it contributes to improving self-sufficiency in F&Vs not only in the Orkney Mainland, but also in the Outer Islands and other less central places. This can only be achieved if various growers across the archipelago express interest, primarily the Community Development Trusts that manage cafés and shops in the Outer Islands, of local Coops.
- C.** **Land** and **Polycrubs** are already available to install the Tower Farms. The intervention assumes that the infrastructure where to install the Tower Farms is already there, and the Tower Farms increase the growing potential; or alternatively, that the organisations interested have access to land where they can build Polycrubs. Obviously, the second option is less suitable, as it would require additional investments without generating positive synergies with the current food growing environment.
- D.** Ongoing **funding** is available for managing the Tower Farms OR the products can be sold for a profit. While the initial investment is likely to be covered with external financing tools, recoverable or not, the activity needs to become financially viable in the long-term. For this purpose, the initial funding stream should remain available along the years to cover input and management costs, or the growing organisations need to sell the product in the market, e.g., in shops, cafés, or restaurants.
- E.** Product **prices** are aligned with the local purchasing power. Our interviewees suggested that most Orkney consumers shop for food in large supermarkets in Kirkwall (Tesco, Lidl), which already have well-established F&V procurement agreements with external suppliers; and affordability of F&Vs in the Outer Islands is already an issue. Thus, market opportunities are limited unless selling prices for the Tower Farmer produce can keep pace with currently available options. Visiting tourists could become an alternative target for selling the produce at premium prices; nevertheless, leafy greens are not a “showstopper ingredient” that restaurants could easily advertise *per se*.
- F.** The adopting organisations can **balance the books** OR get income from other, diversified activities (cafés, etc.). Closely related to the above assumptions, the long-term financial viability of the project requires earnings from sales (or subsidies) and production costs to be balanced, even if the adopter is driven purely by community wealth generation. Alternatively, growers could compensate financial losses with other profit-generating activities such as the sale of other products in cafés, the provision of accommodation services, etc. (the activities of Development Trusts are indeed highly diversified).
- G.** **Volunteering** labour is available locally (for not-for-profit growers) OR part-time **employees** can be hired. This assumption relates to the previous one stating that growers can balance their books, by focusing on options in terms of labour. Not-for-profit growers could rely on volunteer labour, which should be locally available, while those targeting sales should be able to hire full-time, or more likely, part-time employees, who should also be locally available (entailing available and affordable housing and someone willing to move to the locality or, alternatively, currently unemployed workforce).
- H.** The cost of the Tower Farms is **affordable** given the current funding and the organisations’ budgets. While public or private funds may be available to cover the initial investment cost, it will not necessarily cover the full cost, requiring the organisations to identify additional resources. While the cost of the Tower Farms is much lower than that of a VF, we must assume that it does not increase in the short-term, and that either the available funding options cover it, or the adopters can compensate.
- I.** The **technology** can be learned and managed locally. Although managing the Tower Farm system is much less complicated than managing a VF, and some interviewees suggested that a similar system could even be self-built, it still requires some training for local gardeners. Due to the distance of the Orkney Islands from the venues where the equipment is produced, we must hence assume that the system can be managed locally, without constant in-person support from the technology provider.

- J. There is ongoing supply of **inputs** (seedlings, nutrients), and available technical **assistance**. Running a Tower Farm system requires constant supply of seeds, rockwool (the growing medium to be placed in tower channels), and the nutrient solution, as well as replacement pieces if necessary. This creates a situation of dependency on the technology provider, who should regularly ship these items to the Orkney Islands. While this supply is part of the installation contract, we must assume that the supplier remains operational, and is willing to provide this service in the long run, at an acceptable cost.
- K. Some (limited) **energy** is available locally (e.g., from community turbines). Although the energy requirement of a Tower Farm system is much smaller than that of a VF, the pumps for the circulation of the nutrient solution require power; this will increase the energy bill of the growing organisation. Similar to what was already stated for the VF (baseline assumption D), if the same organisation manages wind turbines, the cost of the energy exported to the grid could offset that of the energy used by the Tower Farms; or a “smart grid” could be set up to use the energy locally, offsetting some emissions from conventional agriculture, and contributing to net-zero emissions targets.

4 Contextual Conditions and Mechanism Mapping

The contextual conditions represent the “external environment” where the interventions are (or, in our case, would be) implemented, and relate to three domains: the geographical context (i.e., the specificities of the Orkney Islands), the societal and market context, and the policy context (from the local, to the Scottish, UK, and international levels). In order to achieve their long-term goal, the way the interventions are implemented should be adapted to the contextual conditions, which can represent either “opportunities” (identified in the following by +), or “challenges” (–). Contextual conditions can change with time, meaning that the interventions should also adapt in order to keep delivering their long-term goals. Since our analysis is cross-sectional, we consider the conditions as of the time of the interviews; whether these will change, will constitute part of the discussion of the “most plausible negative,” and “most plausible positive” scenarios later in the project. The contextual conditions are the same for the two interventions, and are represented by yellow circles included at the margins of the ToC diagrams in Figure 1 and Figure 2 (a different side of the diagram for each domain).

4.1. Geographical Context

The Orkney Islands represent a very specific geographical context, due to their remoteness compared to population centres, which increases the cost of goods and services. Nevertheless, compared to other Scottish island groups, the agricultural and food sectors are more developed, although significant gaps remain between Orkney Mainland and connected isles, and the Outer Islands. For instance, 91% of the dwellers in the Mainland have easy access to locally produced food and drink, compared to 60% in the Scottish islands overall, and 55% in the Outer Islands (Hopkins, 2024). Equally, 83% of the dwellers of the Mainland buy locally produced food and drink “often,” compared to 71% in the Outer Islands, and 61% in the Scottish islands overall (*Ibid*). Focusing on F&Vs specifically (fresh, frozen or tinned), 95% of the residents in the Orkney Mainland agree that these are “readily accessible,” and 75% that they are affordable where they live, compared to 87% and 56% in the Scottish islands overall, but as little as 80% and 44% in the Orkney Outer Islands (*Ibid*), revealing the huge impact of transport costs. It must be highlighted that these percentages refer to all types of F&Vs (not only fresh), and especially that there is no information on whether these F&Vs are locally produced. Bearing in mind this situation, below we mention the most relevant characteristics of the geographical context.

- I. *Climatic and soil conditions are unsuitable for growing leafy green vegetables* (–). Orkney agriculture is focused on beef production, thanks to high-quality grass, with some cereal growing (namely, the heritage variety known as Bere barley), although constrained by poor (low-manganese) soils. Local production of F&Vs is limited to potatoes and other root crops, usually with local distribution, and

polytunnels are not an option, because of strong winds. However, Polycrubs have been installed by many small producers around the islands, including schools and Kirkwall hospital, and are used to grow salad crop, tomatoes, soft fruits, etc., allowing (limited) access to fresh foods.

- II. **Availability of low-cost wind energy from local turbines (+).** Thanks to the windy weather conditions, Orkney has a significant production of wind energy through community as well as privately owned wind turbines. This situation motivated the inclusion of the VF in the Island Growth Deal despite the significant energy requirements. Currently, the grid cannot take all the electricity generated by the wind turbines in the Orkney Islands, which are thus “curtailed” (they are provisionally deactivated). This energy could be potentially used to produce food in the VF or Tower Farms; however, direct use by producers is not allowed by the current regulations.
- III. **Remote location relative to major vegetable suppliers (-).** Most of the food currently consumed by Orkney dwellers, and especially the food sold at the main supermarkets in Kirkwall (Tesco and Lidl) is imported from outside the archipelago, relying on external suppliers with which these retail companies have well-established procurement agreements. This situation results in long distances from the producing areas and, hence, high emissions from ferry and road transport, short residual shelf-life (and lower freshness) when the vegetables reach the selling point as well as higher prices driven by transport costs. One of the advantages of this situation is that local produce can be competitive even with production costs which would not be competitive in more central places in the mainland.
- IV. **Fragmented territory (Outer Islands, ferry links) (-).** Although around 81% of the Orkney population live in the Orkney Mainland, and slightly less than half in the main town, Kirkwall, where the cruise port and the main airport are located, the remaining residents are scattered across various Outer Islands, which are connected to the Orkney Mainland by ferry and air services. These transport links add to the above challenges in terms of distribution of fresh F&Vs, which is reflected in the issues highlighted by Hopkins (2024). Due to the harsh weather conditions, especially in winter, transport links can be disrupted, further reducing the availability of fresh imported products.

4.2. Societal and Market Context

There is significant overlapping between a place’s geography, and its socio-economic contexts, which is affected by the former; however, to facilitate our analysis, we disentangle these elements in the MM.

- V. **High local production costs but potential price premium thanks to the Orkney identity (+/-).** Due to the distance from the main agricultural producing areas, the need to import agricultural (and other) inputs, and lower yields due to local climatic and soil conditions, production costs and thus, selling prices are higher than in Scotland’ mainland. Nevertheless, “Orkney” is a valuable brand in food and drink⁶ that can attract a price premium, especially among consumers with higher purchasing power. Whether this price premium extends to leafy greens grown in controlled environment agriculture, and thus not been affected by the specificity of Orkney soils and climate, remains to be seen.
- VI. **Societal openness to agricultural innovation (+).** Research previously conducted by our team across Scotland (Mzek *et al.*, 2025), and even in the Orkney Islands (Dinnie *et al.*, 2026) suggests that the Scottish and Orkney populations are open to innovation in farming, including the use of controlled environment agriculture in food production, and there are no significant acceptability issues when it comes to the products obtained from a VF. The interviews conducted within this project activity confirmed openness to consuming F&Vs produced in VFs or Tower Farms, especially if locally grown.
- VII. **Well-developed tourism economy (including cruise tourism) (+).** The Orkney Islands are a major

⁶ “Food and Drink”, *Orkney.com*: <https://www.orkney.com/things/food-and-drink> [accessed 25 February 2026].

tourist destination, thanks to a rich local heritage that includes several archaeological sites, a beautiful landscape, but also their food environment. Tourists generally have a higher purchasing power, or at least willingness to spend on local products. Cruise ships, in particular, bring to Kirkwall large numbers of visitors for short periods, which cause a spike in demand although with high seasonality. Currently, cruise companies procure their food in the ports of departure, but potentially, the sector could potentially become a target for local producers, compensating for the small local population, and demand.

4.3. Policy Context

The policy context refers to regional, national, and higher-scale regulations and frameworks that drive local development. While the policy context has exhibited a certain continuity along years, mainly due to the stability of the political majority in Scottish Parliament, there are some uncertainties related to global events such as the war in Ukraine and other conflicts affecting the prices and availability of food products and farm inputs. Equally, although Brexit and the Covid-19 pandemic are over, their consequences are likely to be felt for a long period. Finally, the May 2026 Scottish elections may deliver some political change (e.g., a different majority, a coalition government) that could put in doubt some of the current policy framework. Nevertheless, we can identify at least three currently relevant elements.

- VIII. Scottish Government's net-zero policy, and Islands Growth Deal (carbon neutrality objectives) (+).** The Scottish Government's ambition to achieve net zero GHG emissions by 2045, embedded in the draft *Scotland's Climate Change Plan 2026-2040*,⁷ entails a stronger role for renewable energy, including windfarm, and for local food systems, especially in remote and island regions, in order to reduce transport emissions. For the Orkney Islands (as well as other islands), this is reflected in the Islands Growth Deal,⁸ a ten-year plan funded by the UK and Scottish governments to invest in economic growth and sustainable job creation, which paves the way to initiatives like the VF, to which £2 million in funding have been allocated, or the Tower Farms.
- IX. Good Food Nation Act promoting healthy and sustainable local diets (+).** In Scotland, there is increasing policy interest in sustainable food production that could support healthy diets, as demonstrated by the Good Food Nation vision, based on the Good Food Nation (Scotland) Act 2022.⁹ One of the statutory requirements of the act is for local authorities (in our case, the Orkney Council) to prepare local food plans identifying food-related issues, and setting out measures to address them. The VF or the TFs could be included in these local food plans as potentially helping achieve targets around consumption of healthy, fresh F&Vs, as well as community wealth building.
- X. Availability of Scottish Government support for agricultural innovation (+).** As also demonstrated by the Islands Growth Deal funding, Scotland's policy environment is favourable to agricultural innovation, especially when technology can help combine food production with sustainability, and Brexit, with the end of the EU Common Agricultural Policy, and the need to design new agri-environmental schemes, among other things, has opened a window of opportunities in this regard. The Strategic Research Programme (SRP),¹⁰ of which this project is also part (period 2022-27), is another example.

⁷ See <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scotlands-climate-change-plan-2026-2040/> [accessed 25 February 2026].

⁸ See <https://www.islandsdeal.co.uk/> [accessed 25 February 2026].

⁹ See <https://www.gov.scot/policies/food-and-drink/good-food-nation/> [accessed 25 February 2026].

¹⁰ See <https://www.gov.scot/news/supporting-innovation-in-agriculture/> [accessed 25 February 2026].

5 Reflections

We have presented the ToC MMs for two innovations framed as interventions impacting the local food system of a Scottish rural area, namely the Orkney Islands. One of the interventions is the development of a high-technology, high-investment vertical farm, with the ambition of **boosting the food economy of the region**. The other is the promotion of less advanced, lower-cost Tower Farms technology to be installed in Polycrubs around the islands, thus promoting **self-sufficiency in F&Vs and community benefits**. While the second option seems less ambitious, and will not necessarily generate a positive monetary revenue for the adopting organisations, there was a consensus among the interviewees that its **diffused nature** and **smaller scale**, are more suitable for the Orkney context. In turn, the interviewees expressed scepticism about the VF, primarily because of its operating costs, which cannot be recovered, unless a large share of the F&V market is reached. This is difficult given the current **retail environment**. Importantly, both solutions, with different intensities, would generate a situation of **dependency on an external technology provider** for inputs and technical assistance.

The MM part of the diagrams shows how the baseline assumptions are dependent on the geographical, market and societal, and policy contexts. The Orkney Islands' unsuitable soil and climatic conditions, as well as their remoteness from major vegetable suppliers, are unlikely to change in the mid-to-long term, encouraging local stakeholders to look for **solutions for promoting healthier, more sustainable diets**. However, unlocking the opportunities generated by the availability of **low-cost wind energy** is currently challenging, and changes in the national grid regulations are probably required. In that case, production costs would decline significantly, and VF production could become more competitive, including for large **retail companies**, who may even consider managing a VF infrastructure. It must also be noted that the Orkney Islands are one of the few rural and island regions in Scotland experiencing population growth; therefore, their consumption market may become increasingly attractive. Nevertheless, the Outer Islands will still be characterised by **accessibility** issues, which could only be addressed through diffused innovations like the Tower Farms.

In terms of **societal and market context**, openness to agricultural innovation and the boosting **tourism** economy both increase market opportunities, as they ensure acceptability of new production systems by local consumers, and add to the local purchasing power – since short-term visitors are likely to have higher willingness-to-pay for locally grown F&V products, especially with the Orkney brand. Hence, we expect most of our assumptions to be verified. Nevertheless, F&Vs, and especially leafy greens, are unlikely to represent the key selling point for cafés or restaurants. The third market-related condition of higher local production costs could be partly addressed through direct access to locally produced wind energy, while the **price premium** associated with the Orkney label could help in the case of tourists.

Finally, the **policy context** is **favourable** to agricultural innovations that promote local food systems and increase their sustainability, but it is also the most **uncertain** condition, given the persistent **political divide around net-zero**. Therefore, while there is currently available **funding** for innovations like those discussed in this report – and the assumptions regarding their financial viability are (or could potentially be) verified – this will not necessarily be the case in the long term. These considerations call for timely action, and for more, and more effective, **stakeholder engagement** to advance ambitious projects that could reinforce Scotland's rural food systems, and better tailor them to local needs – primarily in terms of self-sufficiency and just access to affordable, healthy food.

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Appendix 1: Interview script for the case study “Novel farming systems in the Orkney Islands”

All interviewees will have received an email from one of the research team with a short summary of our research. If they agree to take part in an interview, they are sent an invite with a WebEx link, and a copy of the information sheet and consent form, with the request of returning the latter ahead of the interview. If the consent form is not returned, we will ask for consent at the start, and record the consent.

Important points to remember:

- Each interview will be booked for one hour using WebEx.
- In each interview, there will be two Hutton people: a facilitator to ask questions, and a note taker.
- Reiterate at the very start that the interview will be video-recorded, and the WebEx transcripts will only be used to refine the notes (so people feel comfortable to keep their webcams on), then start recording.
- If they have not returned the consent form beforehand, ask for their verbal consent.

Guidelines for discussion

Thank the interviewee for consenting to take part in the interview. Introduce the Hutton participants, naming all team members. Summarise our project by referring to novel crops and novel production systems without providing details about the vertical farm and aeroponic Tower Farms yet.

1. Can you please tell us about your role, and the organisation you represent?
2. Do you or your organisation deal, directly or indirectly, with food, and particularly with fresh vegetables, from production to distribution and consumption?
3. What do you think the situation of the Orkney Islands is, in terms of availability, accessibility, and quality of fresh vegetables? Can you provide some examples to substantiate your claims?
 - **Hints:** Difficult pedoclimatic conditions, difficult transport conditions

Introduce the concept of “controlled environment agriculture” as a potential solution to the challenges faced by the Orkney local food system. Mention the Orkney Vertical Farm project, and the Tower Farms being piloted at Orkney College as two promising examples (with different level or technological “control”). Say that we will discuss them comparatively.

4. Had you already heard about the Orkney **Vertical Farm** or the aeroponic **Tower Farms** being piloted at Orkney College, before being contacted by us?
 - **Follow up:** Are you familiar with the Polycrubs in which the Tower Farms are placed?
 - **Follow up** [if they have at least heard about them]: Have you or your organisation been involved in discussions about these project, or are you involved in them?
5. Do you think that **Vertical Farming** has a place in food-growing/the local food economy of Orkney?
 - **Hints:** In what way? For whom?
6. Do you think **Tower Farms** and **Polycrubs** have a place in food-growing/the local food economy of Orkney?
 - **Hints:** In what way? For whom?

Now we will discuss the Vertical Farm more in detail, given the significant investment that such a project would entail, and the availability of funding which has not been spent due to the lack of interested organisations.

7. If a Vertical Farm was developed in the Orkney Islands, what do you think the objectives should be?
 - **Hints:** Food security, accessibility, healthiness, better nutrition; schools, tourist sector, NHS...
 - **Hints:** Do you think that the vertical farm will affect accessibility to healthy food?
8. How could the Vertical Farm impact the organisation you represent and its activities?
 - **Hints:** Proof for both positive and negative impacts, to make sure both are covered.
9. Who (what organisations) do you think will be impacted by the vertical farm?
 - **Hints:** Who will be the “winners” and “losers” thanks to this project? Can you point us to specific organisations that you think will be affected?
10. What do you think the broader impact of developing a **Vertical Farm**, and of introducing the **Tower Farms** on the Orkney economy will be?
11. Would you purchase and consume the vegetables produced in a **Vertical Farm** or the **Tower Farms** yourself?

Thank the interviewee, say what will happen next, including that they will be asked to attend a scenario planning workshop tentatively in autumn 2026¹¹, and offer a way of getting in touch afterwards.

Appendix 2: Summary of the interviews

The responses to the questions below are based on the interview notes and, where not enough information is available, the recordings or transcripts. Where possible, and especially in case of contrasting opinions, the different options are listed, and the number of interviewees expressing each of them is specified. When some questions were not covered, or only limited information is available, “No information” is specified. Researchers’ speculations that could help develop the Theory of Change but cannot be attributed to the interviewees are identified in [blue](#).

Interviewees

1. What are the organisations and roles of the interviewees? Do their organisations deal, directly or indirectly, with food, and particularly with fresh vegetables?
 - *[Part of this response was removed for confidentiality reasons]*. Two interviewees were involved ‘field to fork’ through funding; one was involved in funding some food and agriculture projects, since this is a significant part of Orkney’s economy; one was involved in food by running a pub and café, and they were also considering a community garden; one was involved in through funding, e.g., of community growing projects; one deals with farmers in Orkney, including some who grow vegetables.
2. Would the interviewees purchase and consume vegetables produced in a vertical farm (VF) or using the Tower Farms (TF)?
 - Yes, all interviewees would. However, most said that they would prefer local food from VF or TF over imported food, but would still prefer local, traditionally grown food to VF or TF products. They also said that VF food would have to not be too expensive compared to current options.

¹¹ The consent form already asks for consent to be contacted again for this further activity.

The Orkney food-farming system

3. What is the situation of the Orkney food-farming system according to the interviewees? The information is grouped according to the three categories, and for each category, positive and negative aspects are listed.
 - **Geographical context**

Positive: Orkney soil produces high quality grass, which means Orkney can produce high quality beef to sell at premium prices.

Negative: Poor food security due to remote location and reliance on imports. Very windy meaning it is difficult to grow vegetables in open fields.
 - **Policy context**

Positive: Orkney gets a lot of money from farm subsidies (one participant said it is roughly £20m a year).

Negative: Subsidies are moving away from encouraging grazing – this is bad for Orkney, where grazing high quality beef is currently the main form of agriculture.
 - **Societal and market context**

Positive: No information. [The presence of supermarkets, and external supply chains, mean that in free market conditions, food is more affordable for people than if it were all locally produced.](#)

Negative: People are concerned about the current poor food security, and would like more fresh fruit and vegetables to be produced on Orkney if possible. Market conditions and economies of scale mean that Orkney products have to be sold at premium prices to make them viable, meaning that local produce might not be accessible to all local people.

Vertical farm

4. Had the interviewees heard about the Orkney Vertical Farm project before the interview?
 - Yes they had all heard of it, some had more detailed knowledge than others.
5. Do the interviewees think that vertical farming has a place in food-growing/the local food economy of Orkney?
 - None of the interviewees thought that building a VF was very realistic – due to high setup costs, lack of a site and project manager, the need for curtailed wind energy, and the fact that supermarkets (other than Coop) would likely not sell the produce anyway, meaning it would be difficult for the VF to become financially viable. [Another challenge \(not raised by the participants\) might be how to process and package the produce, assuming that the VF business itself would not have these facilities. If Orkney does not have these facilities, then it could be a similar issue to the lack of abattoir \(mentioned by the interviewees\), where the produce would have to be sent to the mainland for processing, and then sent back.](#)
 - The participants did not think that a VF would be a good idea for Orkney, for the reasons above, and because it would have to be on Orkney Mainland, hence having limited benefit for the outer isles. They also thought it would be unsuitable because VF produce (leafy greens) would do little to address food security concerns, and also has limited potential to be sold at premium prices as it is not a “showstopper ingredient” that restaurants could market. Some participants also raised concerns about the technology involved in the VF, because the need for fertiliser solutions, replacement parts, and maintenance would actually increase dependence on global supply chains, rather than making them more self-sufficient.

6. If a vertical farm was developed in Orkney, what should the “long-term goal” be, according to the interviewees? The long-term goal should link to the challenges faced by the Orkney food system or by certain stakeholders that the vertical farm would help address. It must be realistically achievable and concrete, and more than one if opinions can be listed if opinions diverge.
 - We lack information to properly answer this question since most participants did not think that the VF was realistic or viable, and therefore did not bother discussing the long-term goal in depth. Those who did discuss this said that the main “long-term goal” of a potential VF should be to supply local organisations that value freshness – especially schools, hospital, care homes, and restaurants.
7. Are there specific “constituent actions” of the development of a vertical farm, or any “intermediate outcomes” between the action, and the achievement of the long-term goal?
 - Can we disentangle the intervention “installing the vertical farm” into more actions?
 - Participants said that the most important factor for making a potential VF viable would be finding a site which already has curtailed wind energy, and an organisation to manage it long-term. *As well as this, planning permission and funding to build the VF must be obtained. Then people must be employed to manage the technology in the VF, and to harvest and process the produce. Business relationships with potential customers such as schools, hospital, care homes, restaurants, and possibly the Coop, must be built. Someone might also be hired to deliver the produce to the above customers.*
 - Does the vertical farm trigger a chain of outcomes that lead to the long-term goal? The outcomes would constitute one or more casual pathways.
 - Lack of information on this question. *In theory, a VF would start large scale production relatively quickly after being built, and would then be able to supply local organisations with fresh vegetables. Thus, the above “constituent actions” to actually getting the VF installed are probably the most important to think about.*
8. What stakeholders and/or organisations would be impacted by, and/or have an interest in the VF? List the stakeholders named, and describe the expected impacts, e.g., if they could be interested in using the vegetable products or in managing the facility (including stakeholders for which the impact of the VF was recognised as none or negligible, if named).
 - Hospital, schools, care homes, restaurants were identified as places that might have an interest in using the produce. Participants said it was unlikely that supermarkets, cruise ships, or tourists would use the produce. No organisations were identified as interested in managing the facility. The University of Highlands and Islands’ Orkney College were mentioned, but only in the sense that their site would not be suitable as they do not have curtailed wind energy.
9. Are there any “baseline assumptions” that need to be true in order for the intermediate outcomes to be achieved, and the causal pathways to work? Potential assumption are: “vertical farming products are accepted by consumers”, “planning regulations allow for the building of a structure”, “currently curtailed energy can be used in the VF”. Assumptions might be implicit in the discussions.
 - Participants said that the availability of currently curtailed energy would be essential for a VF to be viable, this is linked to the need to find a suitable site with planning permission. Most participants did not think that there would be acceptability issues with consumers – as long as the produce is not too expensive.
10. What do the interviewees think the broader impact of developing a VF on the Orkney economy will be? Would it help achieve the stated long-term goal?
 - No information on this. Participants did not really think that a VF would be suitable for Orkney.

Tower Farms and Polycrubs

- 11.** Had the interviewees heard about the aeroponic TFs being piloted at Orkney College before the interview?
- Yes, they were all aware of it. Several had seen it demonstrated at the Orkney Science Festival 2025 [where the workshop whose results are presented in Dinnie *et al.* (2026) was held].
- 12.** Do the interviewees think that the TFs and Polycrubs have a place in food-growing/the local food economy of Orkney?
- Yes, all interviewees were supportive of Polycrubs and TFs, and argued that this growing system would be more suitable for Orkney than a VF, because they could be much more locally distributed, including on the outer isles; and because they have lower setup costs and energy requirements. They mostly mentioned the Polycrubs/TFs as an option where the end-users of the produce (e.g., schools, hospital, restaurants) could have their own Polycrub. Therefore, the produce would likely not be sold for profit.
- 13.** If TFs were widely promoted to be installed in Polycrubs in Orkney, what should the “long-term goal” be according to the interviewees? The long-term goal must link to the challenges faced by the Orkney food system or by certain stakeholders that the TFs would help address. It must be realistically achievable and concrete, and more than one if opinions can be listed if opinions diverge.
- To increase the amount of fresh food grown locally.
- 14.** Are there specific “constituent actions” of the promotion of TFs in Polycrubs, or any “intermediate outcomes” between these actions, and the achievement of the long-term goal?
- Can we disentangle the intervention “promoting the TFs” into more actions?
 - Some participants discussed the possibility of hiring a gardener to manage the TFs. Other than that, they thought that the TFs would be easier and more realistic to install than a VF since they are smaller and less expensive. **However, getting a high enough number of TFs installed to make a noticeable difference to the Orkney food system might prove difficult, as lots of different stakeholders would have to be convinced to have one, rather than just finding one site for the VF.**
 - Does the promotion of the TFs trigger a chain of outcomes that lead to the long-term goal? The outcomes would constitute one or more casual pathways.
 - If funding were available to hire a gardener as mentioned above, this could have knock-on benefits in some of the really small communities. For example, if a gardener moved to one of the outer isles and had a family, that would have a big benefit by making the local school more viable.
 - Installing the Tower Farms in places where people could use them, and learn about growing food (e.g., schools) would likely provide further help towards the long-term goal of increasing local food production, as more people would have knowledge and interest in growing their own food.
- 15.** What stakeholders and/or organisations would be impacted by, and/or have an interest in the TFs? List the stakeholders named, and describe the expected impacts, e.g., if they could be interested in using the vegetables produce or in installing the equipment (include the stakeholders for which the impact of the TFs was recognised as none or negligible, if named).
- Hospital (apparently, the NHS already has a polytunnel), schools (some already have Polycrubs), care homes, and restaurants were all mentioned as potential organisations that could install the equipment and use the produce themselves. Participants said that TFs in Polycrubs would likely produce too much food for one person/family, but there could be potential for producers to sell excess via a “honesty box” systems, or possibly selling it on to community shops if they were on the outer isles.

16. Are there any “baseline assumptions” that need to be true in order for the intermediate outcomes to be achieved, and for the causal pathways to operate? Potential assumptions are: “products from TFs are accepted by consumers”, or “the cost of the TFs is affordable for local stakeholders”; most of these assumptions would be implicit in the discussion.

- Participants said that there were unlikely to be acceptability issues, as many people are used to eating food from Polycrubs/polytunnels anyway. The cost of installation was mentioned as a big factor (it amounted to £48,000 only for the demonstration at Orkney College), although several participants thought that one could probably build a similar system themselves for cheaper.

17. What do the interviewees think the broader impact of promoting the TFs on the Orkney economy would be? Would it help achieve the stated long-term goal?

- They thought it would be positive, and would help towards the long-term goal of producing more fresh food locally. *The TFs would benefit the Orkney economy if “economy” meant a system of production and consumption, but they would likely have little benefit to the economy in a purely financial sense, because participants suggested that most of the produce would be produced and consumed directly by the same organisation (on-site), rather than sold for money. This could save them some money in the long run, but might be fairly marginal once setup costs, and staff time are accounted for.*

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This research is funded by the Scottish Government's Rural & Environmental Science & Analytical Services Division (RESAS) under Topic E1 "Rural Economy" (2022–2027). The views expressed are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect those of the Scottish Government. The authors are grateful to the stakeholders who gave their time for the interviews.